

Supporting Information for

Isotopic Signatures of Methane Emissions from Dairy Farms in California's San Joaquin Valley

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Introduction

The first part of the Supporting Information includes additional detail about the calibration method for CRDS measurements, dilution experiment described in section 2.3, an example of a time series plot of the comparison between the mobile laboratory sampling technique using CRDS with analysis of whole-air samples analyzed with IRMS. The second part includes isotopic signatures downwind of dairy farms (Table 4) with time series plots of the CH₄ hotspot, Keeling plots, location of the CH₄ measurements, wind direction, and CH₄ flux footprints of the CH₄ hotspots estimated by the Eulerian numerical dispersion model. The data is averaged to 15 sec intervals.

Calibration Method

As discussed in section 2.2 of the manuscript, trace gas mole fractions and isotope ratios were corrected using low and high custom gas mixtures that were measured before and after each measurement period. The low and high custom gas mixtures were each measured for a minimum of three minutes after values reached stabilization. The design of the mobile laboratory allowed for simultaneous measurements of the custom gas mixtures by both the Picarro G2210-*i* and Picarro G2401. Depending on the availability of calibration tanks for each campaign period, the low custom gas mixtures had CH₄ mole fractions that ranged from 1.92 ppm to 4.07 ppm and high custom gas mixtures with CH₄ mole fractions that ranged from 3.02 ppm to 9.91 ppm. The isotopic values of the gas mixtures were -39.5‰ (Fall 2018, Spring 2019, Summer 2019), -40.7‰ (Fall 2019), and -38.5‰ (Winter 2020). We then used a two-point calibration method to adjust the observations with an offset based on the relationship between the observed and expected values. For the IRMS measurements, we used standards B-iso and H-iso. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and δD of B-iso are -55.6‰ and -247‰, respectively, and for H-iso, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and δD is -28.5‰ and -156‰, respectively.

Dilution Experiment

A dilution experiment was conducted to analyze the precision of $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$ sampled with the CRDS instrument at varying CH₄ mole fractions. CH₄ levels and measurement timing (15 second intervals) were chosen to mimic downwind plume sampling of dairies (section 2.6). Details of this experiment are described in section 2.4. Table S1 show the results of the observed and expected CH₄ mole fractions.

Figure S1. Keeling plot of dilution experiment measurements.

Comparison between CRDS and IRMS Measurements

In addition to the analysis discussed in section 2.4, we explored how the isotopic composition measured by the CRDS changes with different time intervals (30 sec, 60 sec, 180 sec) in comparison to observations reported in Table 1. We found that the isotopic composition remains within the range reported by the IRMS for CH₄ mole fractions below 30 ppm, the reported upper limit for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ measurements by the Picarro G2210-i. Accordingly, CH₄ mole fractions above 30 ppm were excluded from the farm-scale and downwind plume sampling analyses. Below is an example of a time series showing the comparison between CRDS and IRMS observations downwind of the primary lagoon. While CH₄ mole fractions varied across the measurement period, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ remained relatively constant, showing the influence of just the measured CH₄ source on the isotopic signature despite increasing dilution of the plume.

Figure S2. An example showing the comparison between CRDS and IRMS observations on March 25, 2019 from 18:37:30 - 18:38:30, downwind of the primary lagoon. The gray region indicates the time interval used to calculate the mean CH₄ mole fraction reported in Table 1 and the pink line indicates the approximate time of sample collection used for

the IRMS method. a) Time series of CH₄ mole fraction measured by the CRDS. b) Time series of the CRDS $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH₄ observations.

Downwind Plume Sampling

Figure S3. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy I on June 25th, 2019 from 15:51:40-15:53:50. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH₄ mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy I (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy I using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH₄ was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S4. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy II on September 21st, 2018 from 18:05:01-18:09:30. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH₄ mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy II (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy II using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH₄ was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S5. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy III on March 24th, 2019 from 13:28:01-13:32:00. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy III (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy III using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S6. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy III on March 24th, 2019 from 17:53:01-17:55:13. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy III (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy III using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S7. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy III on June 25th, 2019 from 14:02:00-14:05:30. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH₄ mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy III (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy III using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH₄ was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S8. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy III on June 25th, 2019 from 15:17:00-15:18:28. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy III (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy III using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S9. Isotopic signatures downwind of Dairy III on June 25th, 2019 from 17:11:30-17:15:00. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH₄ mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of Dairy III (Source). b) Methane flux footprint of Dairy III using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH₄ was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S10. Isotopic signatures downwind of the Dairy Cluster on September 21st, 2018 from 17:18:12-17:23:36. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of the Dairy Cluster (Source). b) Methane flux footprints of the Dairy Cluster using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S11. Isotopic signatures downwind of the Dairy Cluster on March 24th, 2019 from 14:16:59-14:23:34. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH₄ mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of the Dairy Cluster (Source). b) Methane flux footprints of the Dairy Cluster using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH₄ was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S12. Isotopic signatures downwind of the Dairy Cluster on June 24th, 2019 from 16:06:41-16:12:05. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of the Dairy Cluster (Source). b) Methane flux footprints of the Dairy Cluster using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).

Figure S13. Isotopic signatures downwind of the Dairy Cluster on June 25th, 2019 from 14:14:54-14:20:28. a) Mobile platform measurements of 15-sec averaged CH_4 mole fractions (Receptor) downwind of the Dairy Cluster (Source). b) Methane flux footprints of the Dairy Cluster using the mobile survey shown in (a). The color gradient shows the relative contribution from the upwind areas where CH_4 was emitted. (c) Time series plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a). (d) Keeling plot using 15-second averages from the mobile survey shown in (a).